

Appendix 6.1: Responses to global environmental challenges relevant for Europe and Central Asia (Chapter 6, Section 6.3.2)

There are a number of Multilateral Environmental Agreements with somewhat similar aims although with a different focus. These are listed in **Table 6.1.1** based on purpose, date adopted and entry into force and how many countries in Europe and Central Asia have ratified the agreement, indicating the geographical scope and importance of the agreement.

Table 6.1.1: Selection of Multilateral Environmental Agreements relevant for Europe and Central Asia

MEA	Purpose	Date adopted	Entry into force	Parties in total	Parties in the ECA-region (54)
IPPC – International Plant Protection Convention	The International Plant Protection Convention is an international treaty that aims to secure coordinated, effective action to prevent and to control the introduction and spread of pests of plants and plant products.	1951	1952	182	48
Ramsar Convention – Convention on Wetlands of International Importance Especially as Waterfowl Habitat	To conserve and promote the wise use of wetlands.	1971	1975	169	53
World Heritage Convention – Convention Concerning the Protection of the World Cultural and Natural Heritage	To establish an effective system of identification, protection, and preservation of cultural and natural heritage, and to provide emergency and long-term protection of sites of value.	1972	1975	193	52
CITES – Convention on International Trade in Endangered Species of Wild Fauna and Flora	To ensure that international trade in wild plant and animal species does not threaten their survival in the wild, and specifically to protect endangered species from over-exploitation.	1973	1975	183	52
CMS – Convention on the Conservation of Migratory Species of Wild Animals	To conserve wild animal species that migrate across or outside national boundaries by developing species-specific agreements, providing protection for endangered species, conserving habitat, and undertaking cooperative research.	1979	1983	124	46
UNCLOS – United Nations Convention on the Law of the Seas	To establish a comprehensive legal order to promote peaceful uses of the oceans and seas, equitable and efficient utilization of their resources, and conservation of their living resources.	1982	1994	168	44

Vienna Convention – Convention for the Protection of the Ozone Layer	To protect human health and the environment from the effects of stratospheric ozone depletion by controlling human activities that harm the ozone layer and by cooperating in joint research.	1985	1988	197	54
Montreal Protocol – Protocol on Substances that Deplete the Ozone Layer (Protocol to Vienna Convention)	To reduce and eventually eliminate emissions of man-made ozone- depleting substances.	1987	1989	197	54
Basel Convention – Convention on the Control of Transboundary Movements of Hazardous Wastes and Their Disposal	To ensure environmentally sound management of hazardous wastes by minimizing their generation, reducing their transboundary movement, and disposing of these wastes as close as possible to their source of generation.	1987	1989	186	53
IPCC – Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change	To collate, evaluate, and synthesize data on climate change and climate change impacts on the environment and society. Data on biodiversity and ecosystem services are provided by IPCC WG II.	1988	1988	197	54
UNFCCC – United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change	To stabilize greenhouse gas concentrations in the atmosphere at a level preventing dangerous human-caused interference with the climate system.	1992	1992	197	54
Kyoto Protocol – Kyoto Protocol to the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change	To supplement the Framework Convention on Climate Change by establishing legally binding constraints on greenhouse gas emissions and encouraging economic and other incentives to reduce emissions.	1997	2005	192	53
CBD – Convention on Biological Diversity	To conserve biological diversity and promote its sustainable use, and to encourage the equitable sharing of the benefits arising out of the utilization of genetic resources.	1992	1993	196	54
Aarhus Convention – Convention on Access to Information, Public Participation in Decision- Making and Access to Justice in Environmental Matters	To guarantee the rights of access to information, public participation and in decision-making, and legal redress in environmental matters.	1998	2001	47	47
International Treaty on Plant Genetic Resources for Food and Agriculture	To guarantee food security through the conservation, exchange and sustainable use of the world's plant genetic resources for food and agriculture, as well as the fair and equitable benefit sharing arising from its use.	2001	2004	141	39
Paris agreement	To enhance the implementation of the UNFCCC	2015	2016	133	53

Regional Conventions

Regional binding instruments are, in contrast to global treaties, limited in their geographical scope to certain regions, e.g. Europe, the Nordic, Mediterranean or Central Asia. The instruments address certain shared focus areas and objectives with respect to environmental protection, and functions forms a part of international law. A selection of regional environmental agreements relevant for Europe and Central Asia is displayed in **Table 6.1.2**. The table also shows their purpose and how many countries in Europe and Central Asia have ratified the agreement, indicating the geographical scope and importance of the agreement.

Table 6.1.2: Selection of Regional Environmental Agreements relevant for Europe and Central Asia (does not include EU legislation)

Agreements	Purpose	Date adopted	Entry into force	Parties in total	Parties in the ECA-region (54)
The Nordic Environmental Protection Convention	Has a non-discriminatory approach in permitting procedures (environmentally hazardous activities) where the affected neighboring country's environmental protection interests are equalized. Includes also participatory rights for citizens.	1974	1976	4	4
Convention on the Conservation of European Wildlife and Natural Habitats (Bern Convention)	Promotes nature conservation, covering most of the natural heritage of the European continent (and a few African states). First international treaty to protect both species and habitats.	1979	1982	51	47
Convention on the Protection and Use of Transboundary Watercourses and International Lakes	A framework convention with general obligations (not attached to a specific water system), and parties is encouraged to adopt bi- or multilateral agreements concerning transnational waters and water courses.	1992	1996	41	41
The Convention on the Protection of the Black Sea Against Pollution	To prevent, reduce and control the pollution in the Black Sea in order to protect and preserve the marine environment.	1992	1994	6	6
Convention on the Protection of the Marine Environment of the Baltic Sea Area	To establish a framework of regional cooperation to prevent and eliminate pollution in order to promote the ecological restoration of the Baltic Sea Area and the preservation of its ecological balance.	1992	2000	12	12
The European Landscape Convention	To encourage states to introduce a national landscape policy not restricted to the protection of exceptional landscapes but also to take everyday landscapes into consideration.	2000	2004	38	38
Framework Convention on Environmental Protection for Sustainable Development in Central Asia	To ensure effective protection of the environment in Central Asia, including the rational use of natural resources, as well as reduce and prevent transboundary environmental damage by harmonization	2006	Not in force	(5) signed by 3	5

	and coordination of environmental policies and actions.				
Agreement on transnational rivers between Sweden and Finland	It is an update of an older treaty from 1971 and encompasses rules on the management of three major rivers and their basins, and certain coastal areas within the Gulf of Bothnia.	2009	2010	2	2
Agreement on Cooperation on Aeronautical and Maritime Search and Rescue in the Arctic	To develop an international instrument for cooperation on search and rescue operations in the Arctic. First binding agreement under the Arctic Council.	2011	2013	8	8
Agreement on Cooperation on Marine Oil Pollution Preparedness and Response in the Arctic	An international instrument on Arctic marine oil pollution preparedness and response. Second binding agreement under the Arctic Council.	2013	Not in force	(8) Signed, not ratified	8

Source: own representation.